

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: USABIMANA****FIRST NAME: HONORE****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student used Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references

The author (student) used Zotero to insert references

The author (student) used Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 5%

The author used the following software: (Microsoft Word – Office 365 on Windows 11 Pro-64 bits)

List 5 to 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Academic essay writing style (EUCLID 2021, 7-11)
2. Punctuation (EUCLID 2021, 15)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-34)
4. Assay citation (EUCLID 2021, 35)
5. Chicago Style and Usage (EUCLID 2021, 44)

A BETTER WAY TO WRITE AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

After several months of researching a suitable Ph.D. program for my background and life objectives, the Google search engine prompted me to a unique multi-disciplinary and global treaty-chartered University, “EUCLID.” My dreams came true when I found out that this program is offered online. I feel so excited when I see myself onboard and logged in to the portal to take my course. International Academic Writing (ACA-401-D) is one of the courses I have been waiting for for a long time, as I wanted to embellish and sharpen my professional writing skills perfectly.

Looking at the ACA-401D course pack as it was revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma, I did not doubt the improvement in writing skills this course provides. The ACA-401D course pack material and prepared videos that complement it. Some of the key takeaways learned when writing a good academic essay include preparations before and during the writing process, starting the essay, organizing ideas, using punctuation, using different spelling, plagiarism, and referencing the essay. Respecting guidelines when writing is something very important to the readers and the writer too. A well-written essay attracts readers to keep reading it and, most importantly, captures the message the writer intended to give very well. On the other hand, the author

ought to entertain readers while providing a clear message as intended to spread it. Thus, grammar, punctuation, syntax, and spelling are very important elements to consider in academic essay writing.

In this response paper that unleashes the academic writing as taught in the ACA-401D course pack for period one, I opted to emphasize writing style, punctuation, plagiarism, and citation. I will also base my comments and views on the writing guidelines of other ACA-401D course packs. When writing, I have chosen the American English.

2) ACADEMIC WRITING STYLE

When it comes to academic writing, attention is crucial to contextualizing ideas using understandable words, short sentences, and a writing style that helps readers. Academic essay or scholarly writing is nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work (EUCLID 2021, 7). Nearly all academic writing shares some kind of formal prose register, citations, and references to other works, use of stable rhetorical moves to define the project's scope, position it in relevant research, and advance new contributions (EUCLID 2021, 7).

When the author is about to start writing, one should be doted with a plan with clear writing plan that includes the topic, definition, and analysis of the question in matter, then enumerate key hypotheses to discuss. A research topic should be well-tailored to deliberately provide relevant and coherent development. The author should diligently analyze the question and define key terms after researching the topic and understanding it. One must look at different credible academic resources for further understanding of related ideas from other authors, take notes from the preliminary reading, develop essay plan, draft the essay into main parts i.e., introduction, body, and conclusion and then, keep aside the draft for 1-2 days to review and make change (EUCLID 2021, 8). This interesting writing exercises sinks in the author and helps one to emerge while editing and re-drafting the essay. It is highly recommended to have a colleague or friend to read it. Before handing in the essay, it is super recommended to provide all refences used.

The ACA-401D suggests some rules of thumb for writing a paper to any academic writer to avoid any mislead from the original idea, topic, or hypothesis. One should clearly state the thesis of the paper in the very opening paragraph. One must stay focused on problematic that's animates the paper and should rather confine oneself in the same context of the original position and not lead with (or conclude with, or otherwise include) sweeping generalities. Always, write clearly which means short sentences with page-short paragraphs while paying attention to signal transitions (EUCLID 2021, 13). Writing in academic style, prohibits the author to use run-on expressions, rhetorical questions, colloquial questions as well as phrasal verbs (David 2012, 11-13).

The package of ACA-401D course pack period one perfectly shapes me in a way I will consistently and professionally write any academic essay with confidence. Various aspects of writing tips were assimilated and conferred on me enough knowledge in writing.

3) PUNCTUATION

Writing an academic essay doubtlessly implies punctuation. During the lecture of this ACA-401D course pack, I learned a lot about punctuation. I was very curious to know what really this section embodies. Most people think that they are enough knowledgeable in writing, especially proper use of punctuation. It sounds easy and less relevant to learn how to use punctuation, but this one is the core tool in writing that contextualizes whatever written idea. Without punctuation, a set of words that made a sentence or paragraph would be nonsense or non-understandable.

Among general rules of punctuation, the use of little punctuation as necessary while retaining the meaning of the sentence (EUCLID 2021, 16), remains a primordial element. Punctuation rules include the best use of apostrophe indicating possession and the one indicating the letter's omission, brackets, bullet points, colon and semicolon, comma, ellipsis, and quotation marks. Some of the punctuation rules that seemed as new as is the use of dashes and hyphens. The hyphen indicates that it has a proper use in an adjective phrase before a noun, with prefixes only if required to avoid confusion/mispronunciation, such as where prefixes themselves or letters are repeated (EUCLID 2021, 21).

4) PLAGIALISM

To date, there are millions of books, journals, reports, and publications worldwide since humankind started writing in different languages from different nations and populations across the globe. From this point of view, I can imagine how borrowing texts, translating, interpreting other authors' works, and plagiarising became imminent. Thanks to the academic rules and regulations set to mitigate writing frauds from original and headache works without recognition.

Nevertheless, taking someone's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet, and not giving credit to the author. Having someone write a paper for you, then put your name on it, and give it to your professor would be plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34). To avoid plagiarism, the solution is to properly cite the author or source that has provided the information you are using (EUCLID 2021, 34).

After reading the section on plagiarism from the ACA-401D course pack, I am convinced that it is necessary to professionally write any academic essay with diligence, honesty, and integrity. Luckily, since the paraphrasing writing act is allowed with clear guidelines, I am fully confident that my academic essays will be as clean as they must be.

5) ESSAY CITATION

According to EUCLID (2021, 34-35), there are two kinds of citations when writing an essay. Those are to be considered when writing any academic essay, in-text citation, or list of works cited. The complexity of writing rules, the nature of the topic, and the context justify that you can only cite some things. However, there is a clear guidance of when not to cite. When the information you are writing about is common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas, you do not need to cite it again (EUCLID 2021, 37).

Considering these academic citing rules, writing an essay seems like a good exercise with minimum writing errors by prediction due to acquired relevant information. The evolution of technology and the use of the internet left behind some writing principles, but it is super important to honor the author of the texts by citing his/her work.

6) CHICAGO STYLE AND USAGE

Chicago Style is the style of formatting books and research papers documented in the *Chicago Manual Style* (CMS), 2003, and Kate Turabian's *Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 1996 (both published by the University of Chicago Press). While sometimes reference is made to a "Turabian style," this is simply the Chicago style applied to research papers, revised in the fall of 2006 (EUCLID 2021, 44).

While reading through ACA-401D, I was super interested in knowing much more about styles of formatting books and research papers. Kate Turabian's is among the famous useful style mostly dedicated to research papers, as highlighted in the above paragraph. The Chicago Style and Usage re-explain the proper use of abbreviations, capitalization, compound words, italics, and quotation marks. Not only these but also numbers and Chicago Page Formats.

7) CONCLUSION

At the end of my first Response Paper (RP), I learned so many academic writing traits. Paraphrased, referenced, and ancillary texts were taken from the ACA-401D course pack for response paper one. Doubtlessly, the skills takeaways gained from this course is a solid paved way to my successful academic writing.

The first point discussed after the introduction was tackling the "academic essay writing style," and the following were respectively talking about punctuation, plagiarism, essay citation, and Chicago Style and Usage. My referencing was done manually due to Zetero's technical issues connecting with my Microsoft Word. When crafting this Response paper, I have used some online search engines like Google and ChatGPT not in referencing but, just to have a clear understanding of some words and their synonyms. This is a better writing exercise for an academic.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *How to Write a Response Paper*. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University.

David, Sotir. 2012. *Writing in an Academic Style*. Higher Education Language and Presentation Support (HELPS). Australia: University of Technology of Sidney.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.